

GIWIS v3.1

Groningen Intelligent Writer Identification System Documentation

V3.1-draft

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Disclaimer

The GIWIS program is an exploratory software tool for non-commercial applications in a forensic or paleographic context. No warranties can be given concerning reliability of matching results for handwritten documents. The user is responsible for the collection of statistical reference material for calibration of GIWIS over several years of usage, using his/her own reference collection of handwritten image samples, consisting of minimally several hundreds, preferably thousands of images of extracted, pure-handwriting samples of sufficient and standardized quality.

This GIWIS release (3.1) is intended for 'beta' testing by selected knowledgeable workers in forensic of paleographic science.

Conditions of Use: See end of this document (page 29)

Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek

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Non-exhaustive list of researchers who have in some way contributed to the ideas behind GIWIS during joint-research projects 2002-2010:

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1. Introduction

1.1 Description

The GIWIS system is an application for the Microsoft Windows™ operating system which allows to compare the image of an unknown handwritten document to documents in a collection of handwritten image samples from known writers. The goal is to find the 'nearest neighbor' in terms of the similarity of its handwritten shapes with the unknown or questioned document. The GIWIS algorithms use handwritten shape identifiers that have a solid basis in handwriting research (graphonomics) and may be related to intrinsic properties of the writing process (slant, curvature) on the one hand, and character (letter) attributes on the other hand.

The system is not an *oracle* which generates a true writer identity. Instead, the found nearest neighbor should be considered as a mere hypothesis which is stated with a given state of certainty. The similarity of two samples of handwriting is computed on the basis of the differences in image characteristics ('features') between two documents. The result of this computation is a number, i.e., a single *distance value* for a pair of handwritten document samples. The lower the distance, the better a match. If several samples of a single writer's handwriting are compared, different distance values will be found among them, within that writer, with a statistical distribution that reflects the within-writer variability. It is a basic assumption of GIWIS, that a new sample of handwriting from that writer, written under similar writing conditions, will fall within the cloud of known samples. Normally, a natural writing attitude is assumed by GIWIS, and naturally written alternative documents in the reference data set can be found. However, if a writer produces several samples in a comparable forged style, the forged samples will also be mutual neighbors.

Similarly, for arbitrary pairs of writers of different identity, distance values can be computed between their handwritten samples. The image features that are computed from the ink trace are chosen in such a way that the average distance of same-writer document pairs tends to be smaller than the average distance between two documents from two different writers. After having computed the distance values of a questioned document to all known documents in the database -which is mainly a directory with handwritten image files-, the candidates are **ranked in order of increasing distance**. At the top of the list will be the document from a writer which, according to the calculation, is the best match, i.e., the nearest neighbor of the query document (questioned document). This is the primary function of GIWIS, similar to the concept of a 'hit list' in an internet search engine.

However, it is well possible that the actual, correct document by the same writer is not at the top, but at a later position in the ranking. It is important to realize that even in the case where the target writer is not in the collection, a nearest neighbor will be found. How to know whether the 'top-1 hit' is indeed the correct writer? We consider the answer to this question as a secondary function of GIWIS. We will return to this topic at a later stage. Concretely, the major function of GIWIS is the sorting of handwritten documents in terms of similarity to a query document. GIWIS does not require to learn or compute a 'model' for a writer. Instead, instances of concrete documents are compared: "the sample is the model", in principle.

1.2 GIWIS System Concept

The GIWIS program is the result of ten man years of scientific research. The software is entirely written by researchers and programmers of the institute for Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Engineering of the University of Groningen, The Netherlands. The underlying theory has been detailed in a number of scientific publications. Summarizing, the system aims at capturing three aspects of handwriting biometrics:

- 1) curvature and slant, *capturing distributions of writing directions*;
- 2) allography, *capturing shape elements within the handwritten characters* (letter shapes);
- 3) ink density or thickness variation, *indirectly capturing some aspects of 'pressure' and pen wielding*.

Furthermore, the system is able to compute a number of additional shape features for handwriting which are much less powerful in writer identification but which were historically available before the start of the GIWIS development and which are useful in performance comparisons and evaluations.

In particular, GIWIS implements the HINGE feature by Marius Bulacu (Schomaker & Bulacu, 2004; Bulacu & Schomaker, 2007) to capture the distribution of angle combinations along the ink trace.

Second, the FRAGLET feature by Lambert Schomaker (Schomaker & Bulacu, 2004) breaks up the ink trace in little fragments which are of sufficient shape complexity to be informative concerning the shape elements a writer uses in the allographs.

Third, the QUILL and QUILLHINGE feature by Axel Brink (Brink, Smit, Bulacu & Schomaker, 2011) is directed at representing the variations in ink width in different directions.

The reader is referred to the cited publications for more details. Although the features that GIWIS computes are not directly based on a motor model of handwriting, the system is deeply rooted in the knowledge on movement control, collected between 1984 and 2000 by the 'Nijmegen group on handwriting research'. For example, the HINGE feature can be considered a descendant of the writer identification methods in on-line handwriting by Maarse et al, (1988).

The user interface of GIWIS is newly designed. The writer and document-specific data fields for the data set are inspired by the results of the Wanda project (Franke, Guyon, Schomaker & Vuurpijl, 2004.).

1.3 Usage scenario

The typical usage scenario entails that the user will digitize (scan) a handwritten document at 300dpi. Using a general image-processing tool, all non-handwritten material needs to be removed (whitened) in the image. Then the image is entered into the GIWIS system together with metadata such as unique writer identification code, a code for the document and other known facts related to the document and the writer. These items are based on an earlier study, the Wanda project (Franke, Schomaker, Vuurpijl, Guyon, 2004), on the basis of the needs of forensic handwriting examiners. However, it should be stressed that the system has no claims of completeness in this respect. Additionally, it is important to know that GIWIS is simultaneously designed for paleographic researchers and other applications for writer/author identification.

After entering an image into the system, the user can perform a perspective transform, if necessary, in case the handwriting was not acquired on a flat-bed scanner but photographed from a non-orthonormal angle. A number of basic image processing steps make the image suitable for shape feature computation. However, the user must visually inspect the results of the image normalizations. In case GIWIS is unable to separate the paper and ink colors sufficiently, external image-processing tools from a different provider need to be used for additional preprocessing. An example constitutes the presence of the lineations on a paper notepad or table borders on a form. Such non-handwritten patterns may disturb the computation of the shape features which were designed to handle handwritten ink, only.

The next step concerns the computation of the shape features. One of the reasons GIWIS is called 'intelligent' because it allows for the computation of single features but also **feature combinations**. The reason behind this is that any feature scheme -in any system- will have implicitly attached to it the exemplary type of data it is intended to represent properly. If these assumptions are violated, which is difficult to predict, a match using multiple features will therefore be more robust than a match based on a single method.

For a given data collection, the optimal feature set for writer identification within that set can be computed by GIWIS. This may take quite some time on a realistic reference data set, but in the end the user will know what is the best feature combination to use [cf. Section on Performance, later in this document].

After selecting and computing the shape features, the inter-writer distances will be computed. The last step is the presentation of a sorted 'hit list' of matching documents, with the nearest neighbor to the questioned document at the top of the list.

On the basis of the probability distribution of distances between document (writer) pairs in the image

collection, a rough estimate can be made of the log-likelihood ratio for deciding Same-Writer or Different-Writer, in a **verification scenario** where the user not only wants to find 'the needle in the hay stack' but also needs to decide on the likelihood that the shape features come from the same source, i.e., the same writer. It should be stressed that this is not the strongest aspect of GIWIS. Its primary purpose is to find the best match. The reliability of the computed likelihood ratios is directly determined not by the software, but by the size and quality of the reference document collection. This also implies that the reference set (the hay stack) should be representative for all possible questioned documents. For example: if the reference document collection contains mainly right-handed students from a single schooling system writing a page of text in pencil, whereas the questioned document is from a left hander, is ball-point based and contains just four words from an unknown writer generation (cohort), the chances for useful matching are minimal. It is well possible that an arbitrary sample from a major writing style (same cohort) in the set will act as a bad attractor for that document. Carelessness and negligence of the above caveat will lead to meaningless results. Furthermore, with badly cleaned images, it is possible to obtain a 'hit' on the basis of an irrelevant shape feature such as lineation or even paper structure (texture) when the background has not been cleaned.

1.4 Design considerations

It is known that in many application domains, users state to need systems which explain their results in an understandable, preferably verbal report. This is beyond the current state of the art. We have experimented with explainable methods (Brink, Schomaker & Bulacu, 2007), but concluded that this approach entails a price in terms of writer-identification performance, so that road has been abandoned. Some computer-based writer-identification systems focus on the manual segmentation of individual letters which will then individually be matched between questioned and known documents. Such a manual effort costs a lot of human labor. The concept of GIWIS is: **scan, cleanup and match**. Rather than making statements on individual letters, a distance value and a log-likelihood ratio estimate will be provided if necessary. We know that some users object to a 'black box' approach. It should be noted that the GIWIS system is not a black box: All of its algorithms have been published. Adopting new tools costs time. In other domains of expertise, devices are introduced which need an incubation period before users obtain an insight in the meaning of the numbers produced by the algorithm. As an example, in medical diagnostics, many devices have been introduced, generating numbers which were arbitrary at first, but which could be interpreted as more material for comparison and calibration was collected. In the ideal case, all GIWIS users would annually exchange new data to increase the reliability of the statistical estimates. In the future, new uses can be foreseen, with calibrated probabilities for, e.g., 'a writer appearing at rank 10 in the hit list when there are four thousand reference documents in the collection'. We predict that the GIWIS distance values and probability numbers will become quickly familiar for a regular user. For comparability of results, GIWIS is a fixed-binary program.

1.5 Development history

The actual development of GIWIS started in a Dutch NWO project, *Trigraph*. PhD student Axel Brink developed a graphical user interface in the programming language Python, for the algorithms and tools developed by Lambert Schomaker and Marius Bulacu running under Linux. Furthermore, Axel Brink developed new features (QUILL, QUILLHINGE), specifically aimed at historical writer identification. This prototype version of GIWIS was enthusiastically used by researchers in paleography (Smit, 2010). However, it appeared that the ink-width variation detection by the QUILL family of features is also powerful in increasing writer-identification performance in contemporary handwriting. On the basis of this prototype, scientific programmer Aswin van Woudenberg wrote an integral C++ reimplementation for the Windows platform. The GIWIS software uses source code, exclusively developed by researchers at ALICE.

For some image-processing steps, modules of the netpbm package have been used as inspiration. It should be noted that the distribution of GIWIS is not commercial, but can be considered as 'freeware with obligations for the user'. When reporting on GIWIS, the user should cite the relevant paper [ref]. In addition, we, the developers, would like to develop a reference base of documents. However, given the sensitive nature of many writer-identification problems, we would also be helped much by a regular reporting of GIWIS performance. A standard form will be developed. The statistical 'Same-writer' and 'Different-writer' distributions for pairwise distances are a completely anonymous, image-less representation of your data set: The underlying handwriting can never be reproduced from a single number (distance values) that describes the dissimilarity of a pair of handwritten samples. In the future, we will ask users to kindly provide us with these statistics, such that the reliability of pairwise verification will improve over the years.

1.6 Caveats

The identification and verification of writers is a process with a large number of pitfalls. Some of the risks are similar to all biometric methods: face recognition, fingerprint and to human-by-human identification. Other risks are typical for handwriting biometrics. The following list of caveats itemizes a number of these:

1. *Amount of handwriting.* We found that samples need to consist of at least 100 characters (letters) of Western Handwriting (Brink, Bulacu & Schomaker, 2008).
2. *Style of handwriting.* The main and tested handwriting style for GIWIS is Western (Latin) handwriting. However, GIWIS and/or its algorithm has been used successfully on other script types such as Arabic, Persian and others. Performance evaluations for other scripts than Latin are ongoing. For these scripts, nothing is known about the minimum amount of necessary text, as of yet. The FRAGLET feature assumes that spatial minima in the ink trace are good points for automatic segmentation (fragmentation). The RUNLENGTH feature assumes a horizontal spacing of words.
3. *Image problems.* Residual speckles, lineation traces, paper texture, concentrations of book-worm holes, calligraphy, ornate capitals differing from the body of text are just but a small subset of possible problems. GIWIS assumes that its input consists of a handwritten trace under natural conditions (habitual pen grip, stable writing surface) against a white background.
4. *Unbalanced collection yielding outliers as 'matches'.* Example: the database mainly consists of upper case samples. The questioned document is in connected-cursive, lower case. There is one sample of the connected-cursive style in the database. Under these conditions the user should not be surprised of the GIWIS system response, most probably finding the cursive writer as the most likely nearest neighbor. This problem comes in a number of variations on a theme: e.g, (a) the questioned document is a small snippet of text, while the reference database consists of full-page letters (or vice versa); (b) The data base consists of many ball-point samples, of high quality, originally in color at 600dpi, whereas the questioned document is in pencil, originally black and white (bitonal) because it was faxed at 200dpi; etc. This pitfall can be avoided by constructing balanced datasets, with a comparable image quality and amount of text for all samples. Some degree of scale invariance is achieved by GIWIS but it is better to strive for comparable sizes (ink-trace width typically 7-9 pixels, similar character height across samples).
5. If the *writing style is apertly different*, and several human experts would agree on this, it is better to enter a writer code for that (forged or special) sub style, e.g., "Writer5437.Variant-B" than entering one single writer code for all possible styles, upper/lower case variants, etc., for this writer. There is no magic in GIWIS: If the major style looks different to you, GIWIS will usually find large distance values for a pair of documents, too, and will not find a match with a document from the same writer if that document is written in an entirely different major style.
6. *Context dependency of handwritten samples.* This is a variant of problem 3: It is easier to match two samples from the same document, e.g., two paragraphs by a single writer on the same page, than matching different samples from a single writer but from widely different origins and production contexts, spanning several years. We have done informal tests with samples from a handful of individuals providing samples spanning several decades. Results give an indication that GIWIS is well able to find matches, but the fact remains true that the easiest pairwise comparison is from two regions of interest from one document, i.e., from one page of text produced a particular moment in time with one, single writing implement, other pairwise comparisons becoming more difficult as the writing contexts differ.
7. *Dependency on writing implement.* Similarly, if one sample is written with a very thin ink trace by fountain pen, and a target sample is written with a thick felt pen, the chances of finding a match are limited. This can be counteracted by applying a thinning image operator on the 'felt pen' sample with an external image processing tool such as Photoshop™, before matching. Also, not all shape features are similarly sensitive to the sample differences. In the latter case, the FRAGLET feature may detect correspondences in letter shapes, due to the overall shape fit of letters, whereas a micro feature such as the QUILLHINGE or HINGE may suffer from the unbalanced ink thickness condition for two document samples. Conversely, a highly broken ink trace yields only a few reliable full-letter

samples for the FRAGLET feature, such that the other methods (e.g., HINGE) are needed to help out and regain robust estimation.

8. *Preferred feature combination.* The best choice for feature combinations is, to our knowledge, to combine: FRAGLETS, HINGE and QUILLHINGE in a search. If these results are not satisfactory, exploration with other feature combinations such as BRUSH or RUNLENGTH in addition to at least one stronger feature is advisable.
9. *Prior probability of finding a writer in the dataset.* If there is an unbalance in the number of samples per writer, e.g., one fraudulent subject occurs 50 times, whereas the other writers occur only twice in the data set, this will yield a bias for questioned samples from the fraudulent subject. For serious tests, the number of documents per writer should be balanced: Removing a number of samples from that writer until the distribution is even, and repeating the search for a number of such random permutations. The RANDOM feature will give an insight on the a priori probability for a writer to obtain a spurious (chance) hit, given the data set. The GIWIS user interface allows for disabling of document instances.
10. *Image processing pitfall.* It goes without saying that a proper image preprocessing is a must. Please look at the Firemaker data set for visual examples of what GIWIS considers as 'proper data'. The scaling function can be used to make samples of a comparable ink width and line height. For paleographic identification of the *hand*, care must be taken that the image contains clean handwriting only. Otherwise, GIWIS will quickly turn into a book-identification system rather than a hand-identification system, inadvertently zooming in on paper texture and/or lineation as the essential source of information.
11. *Performance estimates.* The Firemaker data set is 'academic', very clean, with a good, single scanner, from a population of mainly young Dutch writers. Moreover, our research has revolved around this collection for several years. We do have shown that the results remain stable, going to sets of 900 and more international writers. However, also these latter additional sets are 'academic', collected under controlled conditions, with comparable content and page layout. Currently, (2011) experiments with more practical real-life data sets are ongoing. In any case, it is important to note that the reported percentages in the scientific articles and in the tables of this report are obtained under ideal conditions, similar to the fuel-usage ratings that a car company would report.
12. *Verification, error rates and likelihood ratio.* GIWIS was designed for identification and contains a number of preliminary functions for verification of handwritten samples. To this purpose, false-reject/false acceptance curves are computed and shown in relation to the measured distance for a given document pair. The reliability of the probability estimates and likelihood ratios is limited. The user is responsible for a dataset which is large enough to yield smooth and reliable distributions for *Same-writer* and *Different-writer* distance values. Hundreds to thousands of samples are needed and experience needs to be collected over several years to be able to relate GIWIS-based decisions to the correct decisions. This can be done on the basis of confessions, auxiliary evidence, etc. This aspect of bookkeeping Bayesian statistics concerning GIWIS as a tool in an operational environment is beyond the scope of this image-processing and pattern-recognition tool.
13. *Blind spots.* For all the aspects of handwriting style that GIWIS takes into account, there are evidently some variables that are ignored or missed. As an example, writing size variation is considered a nuisance rather than a shape feature. Even with a habitual pen grip, the range of character heights that can be produced by a writer is quite large. In case there is an absolute reference, such as the line separation of lineated paper, and sufficient comparison data from many writers are available, a user may consider to take this variable into account in the total evaluation process, in addition to the GIWIS results. Similarly, word and line spacing or other pen-tip placement subtleties are ignored by GIWIS, which zooms in on detailed shape.
14. *Human expertise.* TheGIWIS tool is not in any way a replacement for human expertise, neither in forensic, nor in paleographic applications. The final verdict should be based on additional detailed visual analysis, for which an understandable and convincing narrative can be extracted, supported by other, extraneous sources of information (microscopy, ink or paper composition analysis etc.).

2. Quick walkthrough

Startup of GIWIS takes a few seconds: depending on the data set file (*.gds)

Startup screen:

Figure 2.1 Screen dump of startup screen

File Options Help

top data panel: data set overview, one image per row.

Columns: Name,Writer,Authenticity,Quality,Identified

more columns are selectable (width, height, file format).

Bottom, interface panel with tabs:

General, Preprocessing, Features, Search, Compare, Performance, Clustering

Three pane groups: from top bottom,

Document

Writer

Handwriting

Additional info

Document: Fields are: input: Name, Authenticity, Quality, given: Width, Height, File format

Writer: Fields are: Name, Gender, Handedness, Age

Handwriting: Fields are Pen type, Script, Style, Case

Fields are disabled if no data set is given.

2.1 Step 1. Enter data set

Enter a data set. A data set is a *.gds file. It accompanies a directory with the images of the handwritten samples of the same base name. Common errors are: Clicking on the directory icon (map) of images or trying to import a single image file at this point, instead of clicking a *.gds file.

Via File menu or "Open Dataset" icon

Opens regular Windows input file dialog. Data sets have extension (type) .gds for Giwis Data Set.

Figure 2.2 GIWIS data set (*.gds) input file opening dialog

The top panel rows are filled with the names of the image/writer samples which are called a 'Document'. The first document is shown in the bottom right large panel. It is good practice to prefix the document code with the writer code, in this manner: <writer###>.<doc##>, for example FiremakerWriter2943.Doc02

Figure 2.3 Selecting a document, document information in left panel

Zooming can be done with the mouse wheel when the image panel has focus.

Bottom left panel: fields are updated as the selected document image (top panel) changes by a double click on the sample item row. This operation is identical to a single-click selection and then clicking on the "View Image" icon. It is a common error to start typing in the properties menu after a single click. This will damage existing fields of another line. Check visually whether the right document sample has been made active in the upper pane.

2.2 Step 2. Preprocessing

Click on the tab "Preprocessing" in the bottom command panel, below the document list.

Figure 2.4 Image preprocessing tab

Image preprocessing steps:

2.2.1 Gray scale

2.2.2 Region of interest

2.2.3 Background separation

2.2.4 Remove crossed words

2.2.5 Unslant

2.2.6 Otsu

The round selector widgets are a radio button. Which sub step is selected is indicated by the black round selector.

2.2.1 Grayscale

For instance, the first item is to correct the image gray scale. In the bottom-right image panel, we see two document images. On the left is the 'original', usually in color. On the right is the gray-scale version according to the current Red, Green, Blue sliders at the top left of the command panel. The goal is to find the color mix which optimally enhances the ink-paper intensity distinction. The default setting is $R=0.299$ $G=0.587$ $B=0.114$ (ITU-R 601-2 luma).

Since GIWIS uses a mix operator, the total $R+G+B$ adds up to a constant value of 100%. Please look in the bottom right image to see the contrast vary as the sliders are operated and select the setting with maximum contrast.

2.2.2 Region of interest (ROI)

Select the round white option field. On the left we see a rectangle drawn on the document image with large square handles (green on top left, the other three handles are in blue). If the handles are not in view, use the mouse wheel or the horizontal scroll bar below the image to find the bounding box. Click a handle with the mouse and hold the mouse button down to drag the corner to the correct position in the image. Do this for all corners. If the document was photographed from a non-orthogonal perspective, the Perspective correct option can be selected. In order for this to work, the selected trapezium shape in the image should correspond to the observed perspective as accurate as possible manually. On the right, the selected and correct region of interest (ROI) is shown as a gray-scale image. If this is OK, we proceed to the next step.

2.2.3 Background separation

Select this operator and click the Enable option as well.

The writer-identification algorithms only work well if the ink is well separated from the background. This is the most important preprocessing step. Errors in this operator will immediately translate to errors in the writer-identification performance. This operator is used in conjunction with the 'Otsu' binarization step later. The background separator uses low-pass filtering on the image to estimate the global shift of luminance, as occurs in bent paper or due to the lighting conditions. Also some smudges and smear on the paper may be removed by this preprocessing step. The resulting image has gray paper shape. The ink should be dark, with whiter shadows. It is not possible to decide whether the setting is OK without applying the Otsu operator (step 6). Iterate a few times between step 3 and 6 to find the optimal high-contrast setting.

2.2.6 Otsu operator

Select the Otsu operator which also allows for scaling the image.

Click in the bottom right image and pan/zoom to see an important or difficult piece of handwriting at a large scale. Each character needs to have enough ink to give a solid appearance with an ink-trace width of nominally 7-9 pixels. A low setting of the Filter_size slide in 2.3 will lead to thin and fragmented ink traces. If the setting is too high, non-ink fragments may be considered as ink. [TESTEN]

2.2.4 Remove crossed words

Option to remove crossed words automatically. If there are enough normally-written words, this should not be necessary (Brink, Van der Klauw, Schomaker, 2008).

2.2.5 Unslant

Option to perform a shear operator if the handwriting is assumed to be disguised by the writer, yielding a non-habitual slant for the script. Please enable the option by checking it, set the angle with the slider and press the Unshear button. The default angle is 90 degrees (original slant not modified). Please note that the operator adds triangular image portions on the left and the right with an average grayscale that corresponds to the original paper borders. This extra amount of virtual paper will have no effect on the writer identification itself.

If the image on the right looks correct in the Otsu setting we proceed to the next step. First save the chosen settings for this document by pressing the icon "Save Dataset" or go to the File --> Save dataset menu item.

Repeat these steps for all the documents involved in the test.

2.3 Step 3. Features

Now the document images are in good order, the writer-specific shape features can be computed. In principle, GIWIS always computes the necessary features for a specific test automatically. If the preprocessing changes, features will be recomputed. In order to see graphical representations of the features Click on the Features tab. The bottom panel will show a visualization of theselected feature for the selected document.

Figure 2.5 Feature visualization example: Hinge

Features are (Table 1):

Table 1. Image shape features implemented in GIWIS

1	Random	Not an actual feature: use in isolation to find the prior probability of a spurious (random) hit in your data set
2	Runlength	Histogram of horizontal white streak lengths
3	Brush	Density of stroke endings and beginnings
4	Fraglets	Histogram of occurrence of allographic fragments
5	Hinge	Histogram of angular co-occurrence along the ink trace
6	Directions	Histogram of angles along the ink trace
7	Ink width	Histogram of ink width
8	Quill	Directional histogram of ink widths
9	QuillHinge	Joint histogram of ink width and angular co-occurrence

When the document changes, it takes some time to compute the feature and construct the graphic for a feature. You will get a feeling for what is to be expected for 'good' data over time, for each of the features. The feature values are computed when necessary. Saving the *.gds dataset file will store the computed

feature values to avoid recomputation in the future. If very large data sets are used, computation will take long. There is no progress indicator in this version of GIWIS. Computing the HINGE feature on 2000 paragraphs can be done within an hour on a medium-level laptop computer. All-versus-all evaluations (See: Performance) can be done within half an hour for such a data set. However, the total computation of all possible GIWIS features and combinations for the first time will require some advance planning for large data sets: The computer must be left on and automatic sleep mode must be disabled. Cleaning personnel in the office needs to be warned in case the computation continues at night, to prevent them from switching off the system. For regular tests and experiments, however, GIWIS is highly interactive on current computers, especially after the feature computation has been performed and stored to disk. The largest data set handled as of November 2011 was indeed more than two-thousand images in the .png format containing a paragraph of text, each.

2.4 Step 4. Search

This is the actual writer-identification test. One or more features can be selected by checking the corresponding boxes. Select the document which is the Query (questioned document). The other documents are considered as potential matches. The distance between the Query and all potential Matches is computed and the best-fitting match is shown as the first item in a ranked list. Small document snippets are shown to the right of each document descriptor in the results panel. For each match, the distance value to the query is shown. Please wait until the last match is painted on screen before drawing conclusions. A distance of zero is virtually impossible. Should it occur, then this is the result of the number of decimals on screen. The internal value will be positive and nonzero. Only in case two documents are exactly identical and identically preprocessed, a zero distance may occur.

Figure 2.6 Initialization of Search: selection of shape features to be used

After pressing [Search], this is the resulting hit list:

Figure 2.7 Search result: sorted hit list of documents, with nearest neighbor at the top. Query was: Writ15201.Doc02. Top-1 identified: the correct document with identifier Writ15201.Doc01, with a distance of 0.167 using the features FRAGLETS, HINGE and QUILLHINGE.

The snippets are clickable and selectable for detailed visual comparison ('i.e., by your eyes') on screen. The query document is shown on the left, the selected matching document is shown on the right. Use panning and zooming to compare the result to the questioned document (query).

Figure 2.8 Compare a pair of documents: probability of distance value for Same-Writer and Different-Writer, The two documents are: Writ1502.Doc02 and Writ56101.Doc02 with a measured distance of 0.252. The red line reveals that this is an uncertain boundary case, with a low probability that the document pair belongs either to the same or to a different writer: the red line is in the middle of the two distributions (blue: Same-Writer, orange: Different-Writer).

In order to provide some writer verification functionality, the accuracy of the results can be judged. The measured distance should be judged relative to its probability distribution in case of known Same-Writer documents and the distribution of distances among Different-Writer documents. The reliability of the distributions (figure on the left) is directly dependent on the number of documents in the test. For reliable test, use in the order of thousands of documents. Use the printed results from a large scale set to judge the distance obtained in the current (smaller) document set. Currently there are no provisions for displaying a calibrated 'population curve' which is based on a large reference collection. It could be realized by having two copies of GIWIS started. With current wide landscape screens this should be easy. For instance, put the GIWIS with the reference document set on the right and the GIWIS with the current target document set on the left.

- The red vertical line depicts the currently obtained distance.
- The blue curve represents the Same-Writer distance distribution (false reject error rate)
- The orange/yellow curve represents the Different-Writer distribution (false accept error rate)

The error curves with cumulative distributions can be shown as well, showing the equal error rate (EER) at the crossing between the curves. If the red line is to the left of this crossing, the risk of falsely accepting a document as 'SAME writer' will be reduced.

Figure 2.9 Enlarged portion of error curves, for the document pair described in Fig. 2.8. In this example, the decision 'different' is more probable, given the reference data set and the document pair.

In this example, the actual distance (0.25) is just within the area where the probabilities of distances for different-writer document pairs is larger than the probability of same-writer sample pairs: It is more safe to consider the sample Writ15201.Doc2 as coming from a different writer than sample Writ5601.Doc02. The consequences of maintaining a distance threshold for deciding Same-Writer or Different-Writer can be seen in the 2x2 matrix below this figure. Select a distance threshold by using the slider. Tests which give a lower distance would be considered Same-Writer, otherwise a pair of documents is considered Different-Writer. The consequences of the chosen threshold are shown quantitatively in terms of the number of document instances selected as, correctly the same (TP), falsely different (FN), falsely the same (FP), and correctly different (TN). Furthermore, at the bottom of the screen the sensitivity is shown $(TP)/(TP+FN)$, specificity $(TN)/(FP+TN)$, LR+, likelihood ratio for 'Same-Writer' decisions, $(sensitivity)/(1-specificity)$ and for 'Different-Writer' decisions, LR-, $(1-sensitivity)/(specificity)$.

- ▶ This is the exploratory corner of GIWIS: identification is the main goal
- ▶ The user interface and visual quality of the graph in this corner of GIWIS are to be improved in future versions.

2.5 Option: Performance

In order to judge the overall performance for a collection with known writer identities:

- choose the Performance tab.
- Select one or more features.
- Press the Start test button.
If the distance matrix was precomputed because you use the same features as before, this measurement will be fast.

The example shows that even very basic, non-advanced features such as BRUSH, RUNLENGTH and INKWIDTH may give additional information if used in combination (Top1 performance: 77%).

Shown are: Top1 accuracy (as %), i.e., the percentage of case where the first hit is indeed the correct same writer; Top10, i.e. the percentage of finding the correct writer in the first ten document hits; Top100, idem for one hundred competing documents. The interface shows how many images and writers were considered in the test. A writer may have more documents in the set (which obviously also has an effects on the probability of retrieval). Table 2 shows the results as computed with GIWIS on 2nd of November 2011. The table shows no 'box plot' or 'whiskers' for standard deviations of performance, since the total set of writers was used and the use of k-folds of, say, 25 writers in ten folds would have made the test ridiculously easy. Please not that the GIWIS is mainly not a 'trained' system, such as a neural network or support-vector machine. A number of internal control parameters has been determined experimentally. These are fixed. Only the FRAGLETS feature uses an internal table of allographic fragments for Western script styles. However, this does not preclude the use of fraglets for other scripts, as the fragments in this fixed, static code book are small and have a shape which can be found in the details of other scripts, too. Data analysis on much larger sets has already been done, using a combination of Firemaker, IAM and Unipen data sets. Ongoing research concerns the NFI-2 data set with original samples collected upon arrest in Dutch police stations. For obvious reasons the NFI-2 data set, containing 1022 writers, with two paragraphs per writer from a similar text as *Page_1 (Bob ...)* from the Firemaker data set, cannot be made public. Tables 4 and 5 show the GIWIS performance on this set as early results, on raw images.

Table 2 – GIWIS Performance of different features on the Firemaker 'Page1' data set, with two paragraphs of text from that page per writer, N=250 writers, n=500 paragraphs, using leave-one-out testing (For each document: 1 query, versus a sub set consisting of 498 distractor documents and the target document from the same writer). Please note that only HINGE, FRAGLETS, QUILL and QUILLHINGE are considered as solid methods for practical use. Top1 indicates the percentage of cases where the nearest neighbor is from the target writer. Top10 indicates the percentage of finding the correct writer within the Top-10 documents of the hit list. Top-100, similarly concerns the percentage of finding the writer in the best twenty percent of matches (nearest 100 of 499 documents).

Feature	Top1 (%)	Top10	Top 100
RANDOM	0.4	2.8	24.4
RUNLENGTH	18.4	63.2	97.6
BRUSH	70.8	93.4	98.6
FRAGLETS	96.8	99.4	100.0
HINGE	97.0	99.2	99.8
DIRECTIONS	58.8	89.2	98.8
INKWIDTH	56.0	83.6	98.2
QUILL	95.2	99.6	100.0
QUILLHINGE	98.6	99.6	100.0

Table 3 – Performance of feature combinations (See Table 2).

Feature	Top1 (%)	Top10	Top 100
HINGE+FRAGLETS	98.0	99.6	100.0
HINGE+QUILL	98.2	99.6	100.0
QUILL+FRAGLETS	98.8	99.6	100.0
HINGE+QUILL+FRAGLETS	98.6	99.6	100.0
HINGE+FRAGLETS+QUILLHINGE	98.8	99.6	100.0

It is very well possible that other combinations will yield, yet higher rates on the Firemaker set. Please explore other combinations yourself. For instance, the BRUSH feature may add an additional perspective on ink-thickness variations and boost the performance in a document collection where that is appropriate. Conversely, too much focus on ink width is detrimental if samples have been written with different writing implements (pencil, ball point, fineliner, crayon), and other features such as FRAGLETS become important to check. Again, it is important to notice that generally speaking, most robustness is gained from using the three methods HINGE, FRAGLETS and QUILLHINGE in a combined manner (bottom row, Table 3). This becomes more important, the more heterogeneous an image collection is, in terms of image quality, writing qualities, and styles. Research in this area is ongoing and user experiences will complete the picture.

Table 4 – GIWIS Performance of different features on the 'NFI-2' data set, with two paragraphs of text from that page per writer, N=1022 writers, n=2044 paragraphs, using leave-one-out testing (For each document: 1 query, versus a sub set consisting of 2042 distractor documents and the target document from the same writer). Top1 indicates the percentage of cases where the nearest neighbor is from the target writer. Top10 indicates the percentage of finding the correct writer within the Top-10 documents of the hit list. Top-100, similarly concerns the percentage of finding the writer in the best twenty percent of matches (nearest 100 of 2043 documents). No manual optimal preprocessing of the images was undertaken. Many images have speckles and other problems. The writers were usually not fully cooperative as evidenced from writing and spelling errors. These results are therefore considered as conservative estimates of performance.

Feature	Top1 (%)	Top10	Top 100
RANDOM	0.1	0.4	4.9
RUNLENGTH	6.7	25.8	67
BRUSH	34.7	62.5	88.1
FRAGLETS	70.6	88.9	96.3
HINGE	75.9	89.3	95.7
DIRECTIONS	21.4	50	81.6
INKWIDTH	22.9	52	84
QUILL	79.2	92.1	97.7
QUILLHINGE	86.1	94.6	97.9

Table 5 – Performance of feature combinations (See Table 2) on the NFI-2 data set

Feature	Top1 (%)	Top10	Top 100
HINGE+FRAGLETS	79.4	92.5	97.1
HINGE+QUILL	84.0	93.5	97.8
QUILL+FRAGLETS	83.3	94.6	97.9
FRAGLETS+HINGE+BRUSH	79.6	92.6	97.1
HINGE+QUILL+FRAGLETS	84.9	95.1	97.9
HINGE+FRAGLETS+QUILLH+RUNL	86.5	95.5	98.1
HINGE+FRAGLETS+QUILLHINGE	85.8	95.3	97.9
ALL (except RANDOM)	87.5	95.6	98.2

For the last test (Table 5, ALL), the equal-error rate (EER) obtained for verification of Top-1 identifications was 4%. The EER is the cross point of the 'Error curves' in the GIWIS [Compare] function.

2.6 Option: Clustering

Sometimes it is unknown whether there are multiple writers of a document set and one wants to find out 1) how many writers and 2) what documents are likely to be written by a writer.

- Select features as before.
- Enter the expected number of writers.
- Press the Cluster button.
- In the panel on the right, the clusters are shown (foldable, press the [+]).
- Two images can be selected for visual comparison at a time. These two document images may reside in the same or in two different clusters.

This variant of k-means clustering takes a number of k random documents as the starting point for the clustering (not a random assignment of all documents to the k clusters).

Whether a cluster solution is stable depends on the number of times two writers are put in the same cluster, at multiple tries. The random generator of the program is seeded with a variable number, i.e., the number of clock ticks since computer startup. The screen dump below shows a clustering result on the Firemaker set.

Name	Writer	Authenticity	Quality	Identified
Writ15201.Doc01	Writ15201	Natural	Accept	False
Writ15201.Doc02	Writ15201	Natural	Accept	False

As can be seen, $k=10$ was used, and Cluster 4 is unfolded. The clusters shows the detected pairs of documents from writers and the visual comparison of a different-writer pair shows the visual similarities. The clustering tool is very useful to obtain an understanding on how GIWIS views the world of handwriting style, from the perspective of the selected feature methods.

2.6.1 Use case 1 for clustering

An article by Aussems and Brink (2009) seeks to explore new digital ways of distinguishing between scribal hands in medieval manuscripts. The study compares traditional palaeographical approaches to hand

identification with computer software to enhance existing methods of scribal identification. A case study involving a manuscript of the collected works of Christine de Pizan (London, British Library, Harley 4431) showed that traditional palaeographical methods of analysing scribal hands can greatly benefit from the use of specialised computer software [i.e., GIWIS, using the QUILL feature]. This study also explains in detail a method for repeated clustering, as will also briefly be illustrated in the next section and in Appendix I.

2.6.2 Use case 2 for clustering

The GIWIS clustering method has been used by paleographers to find a transition in writing style for a number of pages, ordered in time of writing. To this end, the samples (pages) were clustered 50 times, into three forced clusters, A, B and C. Cluster membership for a document was then determined by counting the number of times each document had the same neighboring other documents in its own cluster. Results showed a clear type in the beginning, a type at the end, and a brief series of transitional pages somewhere in the sequence (Appendix I).

3. Conclusion

The GIWIS program, version 3.1 is a 'beta' version, intended to be tested by knowledgeable users from the application domains of forensic science, forensic expertise and paleographic research. The system is by no means a finished, polished commercial product. Please refer to Appendix III for the existing 'wish list' for future releases. The maintenance of future releases will require additional funding.

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4. References

- A.A. Brink, J. Smit, M.L. Bulacu, and L.R.B. Schomaker (2011). Writer identification using directional ink-trace width measurements, *Pattern Recognition* (July 2011), [doi: 10.1016/j.patcog.2011.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patcog.2011.07.005) [QUILL, QUILLHINGE]* ▶ this is the general GIWIS reference
- A.A. Brink, R.M.J. Niels, R.A. van Batenburg, C.E. van den Heuvel & L.R.B. Schomaker (2010). Towards robust writer verification by correcting unnatural slant, *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 32(3), pp. 449-457, ISSN 0167-8655, doi:10.1016/j.patrec.2010.10.010
- Brink, A., Schomaker, L.R.B. & Bulacu, M. (2007). Towards explainable writer verification and identification using vantage writers. *Proc. of 9th Int. Conf. on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR 2007)*, IEEE Computer Society, vol. II, pp. 824-828, 23 - 26 September, Curitiba, Brazil.
- Brink, A., Bulacu, M., Schomaker, L.R.B. (2008) "[How much handwritten text is needed for text-independent writer verification and identification](#)", *Proceedings of ICPR 2008*, pp. NA. ISSN: 1051-4651, ISBN: 978-1-4244-2174-9, DOI: 10.1109/ICPR.2008.4761908
- Brink, A.A., Van der Klauw, H., Schomaker, L.R.B. (2008). Automatic removal of crossed-out handwritten text and the effect on writer verification and identification. In: B.A. Yanikoglu and K. Berkner (Eds.), *Proceedings of Document Recognition and Retrieval XV, IS&T/SPIE International Symposium on Electronic Imaging*, pp. 6815-10
- Bulacu, M. & Schomaker, L.R.B. (2007). Text-independent Writer Identification and Verification Using Textural and Allographic Features, *IEEE Trans. on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (PAMI)*, Special Issue - Biometrics: Progress and Directions, April, 29(4), p. 701-717. [HINGE]
- Mark Aussems & Axel Brink. 'Digital Palaeography'. In: Malte Rehbein, Patrick Sahle & Torsten Schassan (eds), *Palaeography and Codicology in the Digital Age* (Norderstedt: BoD, 2009), pp. 293-308.
- Schomaker, L.R.B., Franke, K. & Bulacu, M. (2007). Using codebooks of fragmented connected-component contours in forensic and historic writer identification, *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 28(6), p. 719-727. [FRAGLETS]
- L. Schomaker & M. Bulacu (2004). Automatic writer identification using connected-component contours and edge-based features of upper-case Western script. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, Vol 26(6), June 2004, pp. 787 – 798. [HINGE, FRAGLETS]
- K. Franke, I. Guyon, L. Schomaker, & L. Vuurpijl (2004). The WandaML markup language for digital document annotation In: F. Kimura & H. Fujisawa, *Proc. of 9th IWFHR, Japan, Los Alamitos: IEEE Computer Society*, pp. 563-568.
- L. Schomaker, M. Bulacu & K. Franke (2004). Automatic Writer Identification Using Fragmented Connected-Component Contours. In: F. Kimura & H. Fujisawa, *Proc. of 9th IWFHR, Japan, Los Alamitos: IEEE Computer Society*, pp. 185-190. [pdf] ISBN 0-7695-2187-8.
- L. Schomaker, M. Bulacu & M. van Erp (2003). Sparse-parametric writer identification using heterogeneous feature groups. *ICIP'2003: IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (Vol. I)*, pp. (I) 545-548. [BRUSH]
- K. Franke, I. Guyon, L. Schomaker, & L. Vuurpijl (2004). The WandaML markup language for digital document annotation In: F. Kimura & H. Fujisawa, *Proc. of 9th IWFHR, Japan, Los Alamitos: IEEE Computer Society*, pp. 563-568.
- Maarse, F.J., Schomaker, L.R.B., & Teulings, H.-L. (1988). Automatic identification of writers. In G.C. van der Veer & G. Mulder (Eds.), *Human-Computer Interaction: Psychonomic Aspects* (pp. 353-360). New York: Springer.
- Smit, J. (2010). "Automatic Writer Identification: the paleographer's new best friend?" *Digital Diplomatics 2011. Tools for the Digital Diplomats - an international conference, Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II, September 30, 2011*, <http://www.cei.lmu.de/digdipl11/slides-rep/Smit/index.pdf>

● The acronyms in brackets, e.g., [HINGE], indicate the preferred article for citing the background of a particular GIWIS feature. The first article in this Reference list is the general GIWIS reference.

Appendix I. User experience: paleographic (literary) clustering experiment

Report

Results of clustering (grouping) the pages in BSB-cgm512 into three handwriting types. One or two handwriting types are expected (type A and maybe type B), the third cluster acts as a distractor.

This analysis is done using GIWIS by Axel Brink, ALICE, University of Groningen, 2009.

GIWIS used the features FRAGLETS and QUILLHINGE.

Disclaimer:

This analysis is a quick subjective interpretation of clustering results. It may not represent the truth. It is intended to give suggestions to speed up further research.

Numbers

The numbers below refer to image numbers on my computer and have no meaning, except that the order is the same as the order of images in the original PDF file.

Nr. 11 is the first page containing old handwriting; page 9 in the PDF file. So you have to subtract 2 from every number to find the PDF page number. (Nr. 4 would refer to the image showing the outside of the book).

Result

Result of 50 times clustering using the combined QUILLHINGE and FRAGLETS feature.

11-13 are type A.

14 is unclear.

15-59 are type A.

60 is unclear.

61-62 are type A.

63-69 are probably type A.

70-165 are unclear

166-169 are probably type A.

170 is unclear.

171 is probably type A.

172-412 are unclear.

413-426 are probably type B.

427-516 are type B.

The two extra pages from CGM-2926 are type A.

Examiner conclusion

Two types of handwriting can be distinguished, A and B. A consistently occurs only in the first part of the dataset, and B consistently occurs only in the last part of the dataset. A big "zone" of uncertainty sits in between. This could mean that (at least) two writers contributed. An alternative explanation is that only one writer was responsible, but the handwriting changed over time.

Note: I did not see the images.

User reaction:

My god, this is most fascinating! I represents exactly what I expected! What I find most interesting is that the change from "probably type B" to "type B" is exactly the break where I thought that the woman makes a conscious change in her writing. Thank you so much, this is such great help! I checked nearly all the breaks between the two types you indicated and it seems so far that they match what I saw when I studied the file. I'm also very happy that the pages from Cgm 2926 are type A, I was also expecting (and hoping!) that. I think that in Cgm 518 it is the same woman changing her hand, as she writes in the colophon that she has written the whole book all with her own hands, so this seems likely. Anyway, a closer study of the manuscript has to be done, and your analysis will be most helpful here.

Bon courage for finishing your dissertation and all the best for your job applications! Thanks for taking time doing all this!

Best wishes,

XqXq Wqwqwq

Appendix II. Terminology

allograph - character shape variant, such as t and T. Allographs produced by a writer are the result of the writing method taught at school and individual preference developed over the life cycle leading to the routinely, smooth production of the pattern at each occasion.

GDS – Giwis Data Set. This is a *.gds file format, in XML. It contains, for each document in the set, the file path of the image as well as writer- and document-specific items of information as well as GIWIS internal computation results. Its open design allows for construction by additional user-written software, for the batch-wise construction of a data set. Instead of the piecewise, one-by-one addition of cases (document images and meta data) using the graphical user interface, a large data set can be made accessible in a convenient way, e.g., using some scripting programming language. The actual format is DOS-style, with a carriage-return and newline character at the end of each record.

Major style – Apart from individual, personal writing style, a larger style can usually be recognized: connected-cursive, handprint, all capitals. Also in forging, some major styles may be identified beforehand, such as, e.g., 'rectangular, depersonalized character shapes as in 7-LED segments'. GIWIS will not be able to find a writer identity across the bridge between two major styles: There is no magic.

ROI – Region of Interest. A portion of an image containing the target material, in this case the ink traces of the handwriting to be identified, against a pure white background, and nothing more.

Appendix III. Verification examples

The verification of one writer being the source for two samples of handwriting is not the main purpose of GIWIS, but understandably, a number of usage scenarios will ultimately lead to the question of reliability of the 'Top-1' position as the result an identification run using the [Search] function. Below are two examples: one of a correct GIWIS decision and one faulty decision, from the point of view of the internal decision variable: distance. In the [Compare] function, a graph is shown with the distribution of distances to be expected from Same-writer comparisons (blue curve) and the probabilities of finding distance values for the Different-writer comparisons (yellow/orange curve). The user is responsible for making the GIWIS data set large enough, with a sufficient number of known writer identities. The reliability of the probability curves depends directly on that number. If N is the number of known writers, we will have $2 \cdot N$ document pairs. The Same-Writer distribution is determined by N distance numbers, while the Different-Writer distribution is determined by $N(N-1)$ numbers. For 100 writers, which is about the minimum, i.e., five times the heuristic of the social sciences requiring twenty measurements to estimate a Gaussian distribution, the blue curve will be based on 100 values, whereas the orange curve will be determined by 4950 values. In the examples below we used 1022 writers (2044 document samples), i.e., half a million distances for the Different-writer curve.

Figure III.1 Example of distance (red vertical line, $d=0.14$) found in a **correct** GIWIS Top-1 ranking in the search for the nearest neighbor of a query/questioned sample document. As can be seen the red line is at a position where the probability of 'Same-writer', blue curve, is very high, whereas the probability for 'Different-writer' is close to zero. The likelihood of making an error when agreeing with the GIWIS decision is very small in this case.

Figure III.2 Example of distance (red vertical line, $d=0.22$) found in a **faulty** GIWIS Top-1 ranking in the search for the nearest neighbor of a query/questioned sample document. As can be seen, the red line is at a position where the probability of 'Same-writer', blue curve, is of medium level (0.2), whereas the probability for 'Different-writer' is clearly higher than zero (initial slope of orange curve). The likelihood of making an error when agreeing with the GIWIS decision is fairly large in this case, for the prudent decider. However, the blue curve shows that at this distance, many correctly matched pairs also occur in the reference data set. This is the dilemma. It can only be solved by taking into account additional human expertise, for instance on clear structural differences in allographs between samples, etc.

Appendix IV. GIWIS wish list

1. Better image inspection in separate windows
2. In [Search]: HTML export of hit list, as was the case in GRAWIS and other precursors of GIWIS, for static inspection of hitlists and images with a regular internet browser
3. In [Clustering]: Fully automated multiple clustering as described in the article by Aussems and Brink (2009)
4. In [Compare]: Better visualization of the False Reject Rate/False Accept rate error curve, using crosshairs instead of the slider in a large graph and avoiding full recomputing of the curves per modification of the threshold, which may take very long for data sets with more than 200 writers.
5. Better marking of the current query image
6. Automatic search and marking of Same-writer documents if these are known. In the current version this needs to be realized by visual inspection of the [Search] hit list.
7. Export/Import of distance matrix for cross-collection computing of likelihood calibration (probabilities in False Reject Rate/False Accept rate error curve)
8. Progress bar in the feature computation stage
9. Progress bar in the performance evaluation stage

5. Conditions of Use for the GIWIS v3.1 software – December 2010

This software is the result of many years of research in handwriting recognition and writer identification by many individuals in several research projects, notably the Wanda project, the NWO/TriGraph project and funding by the University of Groningen.

Algorithms by: Lambert Schomaker (fraglet algorithm), Marius Bulacu (hinge algorithm), Axel Brink (quill, quillhinge, foreground/background removal algorithms). Windows C++ implementation: Aswin van Woudenberg on the basis of an earlier Python implementation by Axel Brink which incorporated the Linux base algorithms into a single program with a graphical user interface in the year 2010.

Goals of this free application distribution:

- To give users in forensic handwriting analysis and paleographic 'hand' identification a computer-based tool which gives an insight into the possibilities of automated comparison of handwritten samples.
- To give, for a handwritten query document, a hitlist of candidate matches, sorted in decreasing similarity with the query document, with the possibility of exploring several state-of-the art image features for writer identification.
- To process horizontally oriented samples of handwriting which contain at least a few lines of text, per document.

It is **not** the goal of this software to yield a quantitatively supported verdict about the supposed (dis)similarity of a pair of handwritten samples. Although there are possibilities to compute probabilities for observed 'distances', the user will be responsible for the collection and calibration of the statistical parameters on a sufficient amount of reference data. We, the providers of this software, accept no liability as regards conclusions based on the output of this software system.

It is **not** goal of this software to process single-word or single-letter (character) images/documents: Hit lists of writer candidates are assumed to be based on handwritten samples with a sufficient amount of naturally produced text per document, minimally containing 100 characters of handwriting.

User will:

Produce a scientific citation to the following article when reporting on the use of GIWIS:

A.A. Brink, J. Smit, M.L. Bulacu, L.R.B. Schomaker, Writer identification using directional ink-trace width measurements, *Pattern Recognition*, In Press, Corrected Proof, Available online 18 July 2011, ISSN 0031-3203, DOI: 10.1016/j.patcog.2011.07.005.

(<http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0031320311002810>)

This distribution is accompanied by the Firemaker reference data set, section *Page_1* with samples in contemporary Western (Latin) handwriting (250 writers, 500 paragraphs, 2 documents/writer). The Firemaker data collection has its own condition of use. The full set can be downloaded from <http://unipen.org>

User will NOT:

- Use this software for other than exploratory investigations in an acknowledged forensic institute or university-based research group. This includes commercial consultancy or product integration/encapsulation of GIWIS within other software systems.
- Reverse engineer this software for the purpose of embedding its functionality in other software systems.
- Pass this software on to other persons outside the direct professional context of the user